

A reflection of using Vevox for formative assessment and feedback in foundation and undergraduate psychology lectures

Laura Jenkins
Loughborough University (United Kingdom)

l.jenkins2@lboro.ac.uk

Copyright. 2017–2025. Psychreg Journal of Psychology
An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Providing timely and constructive formative feedback in psychology undergraduate lectures can be a challenge for any educator. Large cohorts often increase the expectation for written feedback on submitted work even though this is not always the most practical or efficient way of supporting student learning. Drawing upon experience from an educator within psychology and across multiple modules, this paper offers a reflection on how Vevox has been used to deliver formative assessments and provide immediate formative feedback in both small and large lecture settings. The reflection highlights that Vevox can streamline the delivery of feedback, enhance opportunities for active participation, and allow students to receive instant clarification on their understanding of lecture content. While the paper acknowledges that Vevox may have disadvantages when overused or applied without clear pedagogical purpose, it also demonstrates that the tool can reduce the challenges associated with providing timely feedback to large cohorts. Overall, Vevox was experienced as an efficient and accessible tool that supported the provision of constructive formative feedback and helped create more responsive learning environments in psychology lectures.

Keywords: educational psychology; formative assessment; formative feedback; student engagement; Vevox

Formative feedback is a critical aspect of learning in any educational institution (Morris et al., 2021) and it can be defined as providing information to a learner that is intended to modify their thinking or behaviour for the purposes of learning (Shute, 2008). This type of feedback is seen in the form of activities that do not formally contribute to the overall module or degree grade in the course that is being studied. Students are not given specific marks as part of a formative task, but instead they will receive feedback based upon different aspects of the task (Smith & Gorard, 2005). Formative feedback can offer benefits to students outside of the classroom situation and research has suggested clear links between formative feedback and employability in terms of the psychological, education and social benefits (Gaynor, 2020; Jonsson, 2013).

Early theoretical perspectives from Skinner suggest that reinforcement can act as a buffer as to how effective feedback is used (Skinner, 1967). Positive and negative reinforcement can act in a similar manner to instructional types of feedback where students will continue with the behaviour (such as learning) if this is rewarded. Bloom's work suggests that students need regular feedback within the classroom environment, and this can be in the form of formative assessments where students can track their own progress and can look more informally at their own achievement (Guskey, 2018). Moving away from the view of reinforcement, constructivist approaches view feedback as an important way of students being able to construct knowledge using feedback (Lipnevich & Panadero, 2021; Panadero et al., 2018). These approaches have focussed more upon the cognitive functions that underpin learning and why feedback is then useful in utilising such cognitive processes. More recently, the theoretical perspectives have moved away from looking specifically at the cognitive constructs and it is now directed towards students being actively involved in the development of their own feedback, such as in the development and use of peer feedback (Andrade, 2018; van Zundert et al., 2010). Lipnevich and Panadero (2021) have discussed how models have adapted over time, suggesting that earlier information processing approaches see feedback as just for information purposes. Later models from Nicol and Macfarlane-Dick (2006) have suggested that we need to ensure good feedback practices to enable a student to use the feedback and to be able to self-regulate their own learning. This perspective suggests that we need to consider a student's current goals and standards to ensure that our feedback is reflective of that, to support the student in their own learning (Nicol, 2021).

The literature suggests that formative feedback can be provided in numerous forms such as being in a written form in relation to submitting a draft of a piece of coursework, to the less formal verbal feedback when completing discussion activities in small workshops (Fluckiger et al., 2010; Shute, 2008). While this type of formative feedback can be effective within higher education, for a cohort of 300-400 students, this can take a considerable amount of time and effort from the educator, so this may not be the most effective use of time (Weston-Green & Wallace, 2016). Assessment activities can be developed using the Educational Assessment Tool framework (Evans, 2013) and this framework suggests that assessment and feedback must be inclusive. This means that an educator needs to be aware of the cohorts' abilities and must be able to make the necessary changes to differing cohorts and individual students (Mohamed et al., 2023).

Formative feedback has been shown to have many positives in relation to student performance, with literature coming to the consensus that it can enhance student performance (Biggs, 2003; Gibbs & Simpson, 2004; Lunt & Curran, 2010; Nicol et al., 2014). Buczynski (2009) suggests that formative feedback in any education setting has several uses such as allowing a student to reflect upon the content being taught and providing a motivational environment for the student to be in. Lunt and Curran (2010) made use of audio feedback, suggesting that students agreed to finding the feedback useful and wanting more audio feedback in the future.

Often, within psychology, cohorts can be between 50 and 600 students (Sander, 2005) and it can be difficult to provide formative feedback in a timely and constructive manner. Biber et al. (2011) has suggested that written formative feedback is the most appropriate type of feedback to use, however, more recent research Wisniewski et al. (2020) and the research from Lunt and Curran (2010) does not support this, suggesting that other modes of feedback can be just as useful. It can be questioned as to

how educators can provide timely and constructive feedback to students when there are such large cohorts within psychology.

The increasing student numbers means that the ability and opportunity to provide detailed formative feedback can decrease and educators need to locate other ways of doing so. Jenkins and Maidment (2024) provided a reflection on how Vevox was used to increase engagement in large cohorts, making reference to the fact that most previous research had used cohorts of 56–80 students (Greenwood, 2023; Khoudri & Khoudri, 2023; McDermott, 2022). Jenkins and Maidment (2024) implemented Vevox with cohorts of over 300 students, demonstrating the effective use of Vevox to facilitate engagement. Greenwood (2023) suggested that Vevox was an important tool as this was fully anonymous and students felt more comfortable using the tool. It was also suggested that Vevox made students feel like they had a deeper understanding of the content being taught, and this was consistent across the literature (Greenwood, 2023; Jenkins & Maidment, 2024; Khoudri & Khoudri, 2023; McDermott, 2022).

As Vevox is a universal tool that is used both inside and outside of education (Vevox.com), questions remain about the utilisation of Vevox in higher education and whether this could be used to provide large cohorts with the opportunity of formative assessment, and ultimately formative feedback. The systematic review from Morris et al. (2021) has provided an insight into ways in which formative assessment and feedback utilised, therefore the current paper aims to extend this by incorporating the use of Vevox and to see if the previous feedback literature can be supported (Buczynski, 2009; Lunt & Curran (2010).

Therefore, the aim of the current paper is to offer a reflection from an academic who has utilised Vevox within several undergraduate psychology modules to provide instant and formative feedback to large cohorts of students. Gibbs (1988) reflective cycle will be used to provide a reflection on how Vevox has been implemented within psychology foundation and undergraduate lectures as a tool that can be used for formative assessment and feedback.

REFLECTION

Stage 1: Description

Vevox (www.Vevox.com) is an internet-based technology support system that can be used by anyone with an account. The aim of using Vevox is to provide participants (such as students) with a range of activities where live results can be seen. Depending upon the type of Vevox account used, up to 5000 participants can take part at any one time. While Vevox has been widely used in education, it has also been used within employment instances.

I began using Vevox in 2018 when I took on the module leadership role of a foundation's psychology module. In this cohort, there were 60 students, and some students had studied psychology previously, whereas others had not. Since then, I have used Vevox in my undergraduate psychology lectures which typically hold 320 students, with most recent numbers being up to 400 students. My use of Vevox has varied. I have used Vevox with first-year psychology students, during a psychology of the early year's module where the assessments were online class tests and an end of semester exam. I have also used Vevox with second-year psychology students in a coursework-based module of applied cognitive research. Most recently, I have started using Vevox within psychology dissertation lectures whereby the final assessment is very individual in nature and not supported directly by module leaders.

In my lectures, I have used Vevox in a different way to provide students with formative assessment activities and to provide instant formative feedback. Multiple choice questions (see Figure 1) are one of the most used assessment activity, where results are seen live by the students. In these lectures, I post a content related question, and I ask students to select the correct answer. After displaying the correct answer, this then provides me with the opportunity to explain to the students why the other answers may have been incorrect.

Figure 1

An example of using a Vevox Multiple-Choice Question in a Psychology of the Early Years exam-based module.

Vevox does offer a word-cloud activity (see Figure 2) that allows students to discuss a question before posting a response, and this is one type of activity I use when asking students to critically discuss a topic.

Figure 2

An example of using a Vevox Word Cloud Question in an Applied Cognitive Research coursework-based module.

If I am looking for longer responses from a cohort, I will use the Vevox question and answer (Q&A) function (see Figure 3) as this allows me to post a question and students can respond in a many or a few words as needed.

Figure 3

An example of using a Vevox Q&A session in a Cognitive Research coursework and exam-based module.

In previous years, I have attempted to use numerous formative assessment and feedback activities such as online class quizzes, direct questions to students in a lecture, traditional hands-up activities alongside student-led discussions (Carrero et al., 2007; Jenkins, 2014). While the literature suggests these to be effective, I have often found these to be less effective as students are often concerned about being identified with their responses. Vevox, on the other hand, is fully anonymous and there are no names or personal details associated with the responses.

Stage 2: Feeling

When I first started using Vevox in 2018, I was unsure about the appropriate time to add in a lecture activity and focussed solely on the fact that students can lose focus after 10 minutes (Bunce et al., 2010). Wilson and Korn (2007) have questioned whether students' attention in lectures can span more than 10 minutes, so I wanted to add in enough Vevox activities to ensure that attention did not move away from the lecture. I took the view of students being active learners as this was a key theme within the pedagogical literature (Andrade, 2018; Nicol and Mcfarlane-Dick (2006; van Zundert et al., 2010) so I wanted to ensure that all Vevox activities made the students actively involved. I was apprehensive about using a new tool, but I did find that the support from Vevox was informative and helpful. Vevox has a Vevox community (Vevox, 2024) that allows users to post questions when needed and receive support. I wanted to provide students with the opportunity to be engaged in their learning (Leach & Zepke, 2011) as this was evidenced a positive in the literature, but I also wanted the opportunity to provide students with written feedback as this has been shown to be most effective (Biber et al., 2011) and this is something that Vevox can do.

During the lectures, students took part in the formative assessment activities even though there was no grade attached to these activities. This was consistent with the formative feedback literature which explained that students to take part if they feel that the feedback is useful and the activity is interesting (Buczynski, 2009; Nicol, 2021).

Working in higher education, I was aware that students can be reluctant to take part in activities if there is no final grade attached (Liu & Littlewood., 1997; Wijaya, 2015), however, at first, this was not the case with my use of Vevox, so I was motivated to continue using it. It has been shown that if a lecturer is motivated and expresses such positive behaviours then this reflects upon the student's

motivation (Noori et al., 2020) so I ensured that I was demonstrated my motivation when using a new tool.

As I have now used Vevox in multiple modules, across cohorts and across class sizes, I feel more confident in using the tool and judging when to add in Vevox formative assessment activities. I do feel as though it is as successful as other tools in the literature such as Mentimeter or Kahoot (Gokbulut, 2020). I am now less apprehensive when choosing to use Vevox as this does have pedagogical support behind the use of tool (Jenkins & Maidment, 2024; Khoudri & Khoudri, 2023; Lyttle, 2023; McDermott, 2022).

Stage 3: Evaluation

As I am now reaching my 8th year of using Vevox within my lectures to provide formative assessments and instant formative feedback, I have been able to identify aspects that have worked well with Vevox and aspects that have not worked well. Vevox has been shown to increase engagement as it encourages active participation (Golden, 2023; McDermott, 2022), however, it also does come with improvements such as the lecturer needing to give more time for answers (Golden, 2023). When I lecture, I try to give the students enough response time and I will often incorporate this with discussion activities to allow students to have more time to respond (Bligh & Cameron, 2000; Zhao & Potter, 2016).

Certain formative assessment activities work more positively than others within different situations so there is no “one size fits all” approach into how and where to use Vevox and this was evidenced from the literature (Gibbs & Simpson, 2004; Lunt & Curran, 2010). With large cohorts, I use multiple choice questions or word cloud activities to allow all responses to be displayed (similar to Greenwood, 2023). However, some activities such as the pin-on activities (where participants place a pin on an image) have most effectively been used in smaller classes. Jenkins and Maidment (2024) provides guidance on the activities that are most appropriate for different class sizes, and this is consistent with the cohorts I have also used.

While teaching the larger cohort modules, I have found that students complete the first few Vevox formative assessment activities with no issues, but after providing a few activities to students, participation rates decrease and attention decreases (Wilson & Korn, 2007), and this is something that I have tried to address when giving students activities that can provide formative feedback. Distractions in lectures can be seen to impact learning (Zureick et al., 2018) therefore this will be the same when providing activities for formative feedback.

I use Vevox to provide formative feedback activities for four main reasons: (1) Vevox makes giving feedback more interesting; (2) Students can see live results and can be provided with instant formative feedback; (3) Staff can access results in the Vevox dashboard at a later date to reflect upon whether any further support is needed for the cohort; and (4) Vevox makes giving feedback less formal by providing less exam-style questions.

Stage 4: Analysis

While feedback during the lectures was a vital part of learning as it helps students to modify their own learning (Morris et al., 2021; Shute, 2008), I noticed that during some longer lectures, engagement within the Vevox activities would begin to decrease and this was consistent with previous research (Bunce et al., 2010). After researching the area of participant and engagement, I realised that it is completely normal for engagement rates to decrease (Offer et al., 2019) and this is something I have been able to try and avoid during my lectures. When students attend in-person, I now highlight the importance of the lecture in relation to the summative assessment at the end of the module and I often find that this does help (Smith & Marbach-Ad, 2010). Students can then see how the lecture content and activities will support the development of the final summative assessment. It has been suggested that lectures being held in-person or online may only help if exams are online and computer based (Fireman et al., 2023). Providing students with positive reinforcement (Skinner,

1967) does support a student's learning experiences, however each student may have different needs when learning therefore a range of feedback modes can be useful such as the written version on Vevox alongside my verbal feedback discussing responses (Wisniewski et al., 2020)

From this reflection, I have been able to discuss with colleagues and give workshop talks on the most effective times and situations to provide students with Vevox activities and to provide the instant formative feedback. Morris et al. (2021) have suggested that students should be made aware of when formative assessments will take place, the type of feedback that will be given and understand why the tasks are important, therefore this is something I now do.

When I was initially using Vevox in 2018–2019, I did not explain to students why it was being used and I just assumed that students saw the activities as being able to provide formative feedback. Students do need to know when and how they are receiving feedback (Gaynor, 2020; Jonsson, 2013) and how each part of the task may link to the end assessment. At the beginning of each module, I explain to students why Vevox is being used, and I always ensure that I use the terms formative assessment and formative feedback. Ensuring that students know the when, why and how of the formative feedback is being given has been a key part of developing my own teaching style (Morris et al., 2021).

Stage 5: Conclusions

Overall, I do feel as though using Vevox for formative assessment and formative feedback has been (and is continuing to be) a positive addition to my lectures and this was supported by the previous paper (Jenkins & Maidment, 2024). These views are also consistent with previous literature on interactive tools (Biggs, 2003; Gibbs & Simpson, 2004; Lunt & Curran, 2010; Nicol et al., 2014). While Vevox does have lots of positives, we have to be mindful not to cause fatigue within students who regularly attend lectures, and to do this, a range of Vevox activities can be used at different times (Bunce et al., 2010; Wilson & Korn, 2007). I have used other activities previously, such as hand-up and discussion activities, and Mentimeter (Vallely & Gibson., 2018). These have not been as successful as Vevox (see Jenkins and Maidment, 2024 for further information). The next stage of my research will look at gathering student perceptions of the use of Vevox for a formative assessment and feedback method and details of this can be seen in the action plan.

Stage 6: Action Plan

The main action plan that I now have is to collect data from students on the formative feedback given in lectures and whether they do use this feedback or find it useful. This will support the author in adapting the use of Vevox if it is needed for formative assessment and feedback. Research has suggested that attendance does increase if lectures are engaging (Cofaigh & Rodgers, 2025; Edwards & Clinton, 2019; Rissanen, 2018) but I would like to see if this is the case for lectures that use Vevox for formative assessments and feedback.

The plan is to use large psychology cohorts from UK higher education institutions. During August 2025–October 2025, ethical approval will be sought, and I will seek collaborators from other higher education institutions.

From October 2025 the investigation will develop both online questionnaires and focus group interview schedules to enable both qualitative and quantitative data to be collected. First, the online questionnaire will be sent out through higher education institutions, and this will ask students for their perceptions of Vevox and if they find it useful. Focus groups will then be conducted to expand upon the quantitative data and to gain an in-depth insight upon whether students find the use of Vevox a positive aspect of their university education, in relation to receiving feedback in lectures, and also in relation to whether being given formative assessments through Vevox is useful. By April 2026, the data will be analysis using statistical analyses and thematic analysis before dissemination will begin.

The investigation will aim to look more in-depth at whether students find the formative assessment and feedback activities useful, in particular in relation to specific module types. For example, whether an exam-based module is perceived as differently to a coursework-based module, and this can be done by making a note of the module types that each student is referring to.

Previous research (Istijanto & Nathalie, 2024) has suggested that aspects such as social interaction and learning effectiveness can positively influence engagement in lectures, therefore the investigation aims to see if a similar pattern of results can occur with the use of Vevox in lectures. Similarly, recent research from Rizwan et al. (2025) has suggested that academic performance may encourage students to engage, therefore it would be interesting to see if formative assessment tools can have a similar impact on a less formal assessment approach.

The investigation will specifically look at the perceptions of Vevox. Vevox has been shown to be an effective educational tool (Jenkins & Maidment, 2024; Lyttle, 2023; Khoudri & Khoudri, 2023; McDermott, 2022) however this research has limited discussion on why students actively engage in the tool. Conducting focus groups with undergraduate psychology students would give a greater understanding of why the tool is widely accepted by the student population, similar to other applications such as Kahoot or Mentimeter (Gokbulut, 2020).

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Loughborough University

REFERENCES

- Andrade, H. (2018). "Feedback in the Context of Self-Assessment," in Lipnevich Cambridge Handbook of Instructional Feedback. Editors A. A. Lipnevich and J. K. Smith (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press), 376–408.
- Biber, D., Nekrasova, T., & Horn, B. (2011). The effectiveness of feedback for L1- English and L2- writing development: A meta-analysis. *ETS Research Report Series*, 2011(1), 1–110. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2333-8504.2011.tb02241.x>
- Biggs, J. (2003). Aligning teaching and assessing to course objectives. *Teaching and learning in higher education: New trends and innovations*, 2(4), 13–17.
- Bligh, D., & Cameron, B. J. (2000). What's the use of lectures?. *The Canadian Journal of Higher Education*, 30(1), 192–196.
- Buczynski, S. (2009). Formative feedback stimulates students' thinking and provides teachers with information to guide future instruction. *Tips for Providing Formative Feedback*, 10, 1–2.
- Bunce, D. M., Flens, E. A., & Neiles, K. Y. (2010). How long can students pay attention in class? A study of student attention decline using clickers. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 87(12), 1438–1443. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed100409p>
- Carrero, E., Gomar, C., Penzo, W., & Rull, M. (2007). Comparison between lecture-based approach and case/problem-based learning discussion for teaching pre-anaesthetic assessment. *European journal of anaesthesiology*, 24(12), 1008–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0265021506002304>
- Cofaigh, É. Ó., & Rodgers, O. (2025). Does anyone still want to go to lectures? Student perceptions of the face-to-face lecture in an Irish university. *Irish Educational Studies*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2025.2453737>
- Edwards, M. R., & Clinton, M. E. (2019). A study exploring the impact of lecture capture availability and lecture capture usage on student attendance and attainment. *Higher Education*, 77, 403–421. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-018-0275-9>
- Evans, C. (2013). Making sense of assessment feedback in higher education. *Review of Educational Research*, 83(1), 70–120. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654312474350>
- Fireman, E. S., Donnini, Z. S., Weissman, M. B., & Eck, D. J. (2023). Do most students need in-person lectures? A study of a large statistics class. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 51(4), 476–502. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00472395231166592>
- Fluckiger, J., Vigil, Y. T. Y., Pasco, R., & Danielson, K. (2010). Formative feedback: Involving students as partners in assessment to enhance learning. *College teaching*, 58(4), 136–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87567555.2010.484031>
- Gaynor, J. W. (2020). Peer review in the classroom: Student perceptions, peer feedback quality and the role of assessment. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 45(5), 758–775. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2019.1697424>
- Gibbs, G. (1988). *Learning by Doing: A guide to teaching and learning methods*. Further Education Unit. Oxford Polytechnic: Oxford.
- Gibbs, G., & Simpson, C. (2004). Does your assessment support your students' learning. *Journal of Teaching and learning in Higher Education*, 1(1), 1–30.
- Gokbulut, B. (2020). The effect of Mentimeter and Kahoot applications on university students'e-learning. *World journal on educational technology: current Issues*, 12(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.18844/wjet.v12i2.4814>
- Golden, W. (2023). Student Response Systems: enabler of active learning in a large class. <https://doi.org/10.4995/head23.2023.16207>
- Greenwood, J. (2023). Ready player one: Using Vevox to elicit student participation in lectures. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, (27). <https://doi.org/10.47408/jldhe.vi27.935>
- Guskey, T. R. (2018). "Feedback, Correctives, and the Use of Pre-assessments," in *The Cambridge Handbook of Instructional Feedback*. Cambridge University Press, 432–450. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316832134.021>
- Istijanto, & Nathalie, C. C. (2024). Factors influencing student engagement and intention to attend lectures. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2415287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2024.2415287>
- Jenkins, A. (2014). Active learning in structured lectures. In *Teaching large classes in higher education* (pp. 63–77). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315041384-9>

- Jenkins, L., & Maidment, D. (2024). A reflection on using an online polling and Q&A platform as a method of engagement in undergraduate psychology lectures. *Psychology Teaching Review*, 30(2), 40–52. <https://doi.org/10.53841/bpsptr.2024.30.2.40>
- Jonsson, A. (2013). Facilitating productive use of feedback in higher education. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 14(1), 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787412467125>
- Khoudri, I., & Khoudri, A. (2023). Examining the influence of gamification on the enjoyment, engagement, and motivation of secondary school students: A case study of Vevox. *International Journal of Current Educational Studies*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijces.77>
- Leach, L., & Zepke, N. (2011). Engaging students in learning: A review of a conceptual organiser. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 30(2), 193–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2010.509761>
- Lipnevich, A. A., & Panadero, E. (2021, December). A review of feedback models and theories: Descriptions, definitions, and conclusions. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 720195). Frontiers. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.720195>
- Liu, N. F., & Littlewood, W. (1997). Why do many students appear reluctant to participate in classroom learning discourse?. *System*, 25(3), 371–384. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0346-251x\(97\)00029-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0346-251x(97)00029-8)
- Lunt, T., & Curran, J. (2010). 'Are you listening please?' The advantages of electronic audio feedback compared to written feedback. *Assessment & evaluation in higher education*, 35(7), 759–769. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930902977772>
- Lyttle, D. (2023, May). Using Vevox to enhance student engagement in an online neuroscience course. In *European Association of Neuroscience Nurses Congress 2023*.
- McDermott, G. (2022). Using Vevox Live Polling As A Formative Assessment Tool. *Compendium of Active Learning & Assessment for Student Engagement*. Vol. 2
- Mohamed, N. H., Beckstein, A., Winship, G., Ashraf Khan Mou, T., Pang, N. T. P., & Relajo-Howell, D. (2023). Effects of self-expressive writing as a therapeutic method to relieve stress among university students. *Journal of Poetry Therapy*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08893675.2023.2174678>
- Morris, R., Perry, T., & Wardle, L. (2021). Formative assessment and feedback for learning in higher education: A systematic review. *Review of Education*, 9(3), e3292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3292>
- Nicol, D. (2021). The Power of Internal Feedback: Exploiting Natural Comparison Processes. *Assess. Eval. Higher Education* 46 (5), 756–778. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2020.1823314>
- Nicol, D. J., and Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). Formative Assessment and Selfregulated Learning: A Model and Seven Principles of Good Feedback Practice. *Stud. Higher Educ.* 31 (2), 199–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075070600572090>
- Nicol, D., Thomson, A., & Breslin, C. (2014). Rethinking feedback practices in higher education: a peer review perspective. *Assessment & evaluation in higher education*, 39(1), 102–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2013.795518>
- Noori, A. Q., Said, H., Nor, F. M., & Abd Ghani, F. (2020). The relationship between university lecturers' behaviour and students' motivation. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(11C), 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.082303>
- Offer, K., Wesson, M., McGaughey, F., Skead, N., & Elphick, L. (2019). 'Why Bother if the Students Don't?' The Impact of Declining Student Attendance at Lectures on Law Teacher Wellbeing. *Wellness for Law: Making Wellness Core Business* (LexisNexis, 2019), 65.
- Panadero, E., Andrade, H., & Brookhart, S. (2018). Fusing Self-Regulated Learning and Formative Assessment: A Roadmap of where We Are, How We Got Here, and where We Are Going. *Aust. Educ. Res.* 45 (1), 13–31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-018-0258-y>
- Rissanen, A. (2018). Student engagement in large classroom: the effect on grades, attendance and student experiences in an undergraduate biology course. *Canadian Journal of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 18, 136–153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42330-018-0015-2>
- Rizwan, S., Nee, C. K., & Garfan, S. (2025). Identifying the Factors Affecting Student Academic Performance and Engagement Prediction in MOOC using Deep Learning: A Systematic Literature Review. *IEEE Access*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2025.3533915>
- Sander, P. (2005). Increasing student numbers: Diminishing tutor insight? *Psychology Learning & Teaching*, 4(1), 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.2304/plat.2004.4.1.15>

- Shute, V. J. (2008). Focus on formative feedback. *Review of educational research*, 78(1), 153–189. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654307313795>
- Skinner, B. F. (1967). BF Skinner.
- Smith, A. C., & Marbach-Ad, G. (2010). Learning outcomes with linked assessments—an essential part of our regular teaching practice. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education*, 11(2), 123–129. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v11i2.217>
- Smith, E., & Gorard, S. (2005). 'They don't give us our marks': the role of formative feedback in student progress. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 12(1), 21–38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594042000333896>
- Valley, K. S. A., & Gibson, P. (2018). Effectively Engaging Students on their Devices with the use of Mentimeter. *Compass: Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 11(2).
- van Zundert, M., Sluijsmans, D., & van Merriënboer, J. (2010). Effective Peer Assessment Processes: Research Findings and Future Directions. *Learn. Instruction* 20 (4), 270–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2009.08.004>
- Vevox. (2024, January 02). The Vevox Community. <http://www.vevox.com/community>
- Weston-Green, K., & Wallace, M. (2016). A method of providing engaging formative feedback to large cohort first-year physiology and anatomy students. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 40(3), 393–397. <https://doi.org/10.1152/advan.00174.2015>
- Wijaya, T. B. W. (2015). *Factors Contributing to Students' Reluctance To Participate In English Class* (Doctoral dissertation, Program Studi Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris FBS–UKSW).
- Wilson, K., & Korn, J. H. (2007). Attention during lectures: Beyond ten minutes. *Teaching of Psychology*, 34(2), 85–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986280701291291>
- Wisniewski, B., Zierer, K., & Hattie, J. (2020). The power of feedback revisited: A meta-analysis of educational feedback research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 3087. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.03087>
- Zhao, B., & Potter, D. D. (2016). Comparison of lecture-based learning vs discussion-based learning in undergraduate medical students. *Journal of surgical education*, 73(2), 250–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2015.09.016>
- Zureick, A. H., Burk-Rafel, J., Purkiss, J. A., & Hortsch, M. (2018). The interrupted learner: How distractions during live and video lectures influence learning outcomes. *Anatomical sciences education*, 11(4), 366–376. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ase.1754>